

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Applying farmyard manure and incorporating cover crops resulted in best economic performance in organic arable farming

Most agricultural land in Flanders shows a high soil P-status. This seems to counteract microbial activity in the rhizosphere, on which organic growers rely as a plant feeding mechanism. A trial at ILVO aimed to explore strategies that may contribute to soil quality and N-supply, while reducing P-surplus. N:P and C:P ratios of farmyard manure (FYM) were modified by co-composting it with 'brown' material. In the same trial, cover crops (CC) were either destroyed and incorporated versus mowed and removed. Following treatments were applied to organic potato (2020), CC, winter leek (2021, not in this study), summer barley (2022), CC, and savoy cabbage (2023).

- T1: no fertilization + CC in.
- T2: no fertilization + CC off.
- T3: FYM + CC in.
- T4: FYM + CC off.
- T5: compost + CC in.
- T6: compost + CC off.

In general, direct costs only varied 1 or 2% between the treatments. For fertilization only the fuel cost for spreading was accounted for. In this case, the manure came for free, as it was exchanged for grass-clover harvested from another plot. Removing the cover crop did entail additional fuel and labour costs, but selling it as feed also generated extra revenues.

Crop yields, however, varied considerably. They were higher when applying stockpiled farmyard manure than when using compost (and 'no FYM'), which we can attribute directly to the fertilizer working coefficient (active nitrogen farmyard manure > compost). In addition, removing the cover crop resulted in lower yields. This was most evident in savoy cabbage and potatoes, as these crops require a lot of nitrogen.

Over the 3 trial years gross margins were T3 > T4 (-18%) > T5 (-24%) > T6 (-35%) > T1 (-38%) > T2 (-44%). Higher yields resulted in higher sales revenues and also in higher gross margins.

1. Revenue, direct cost and gross margin (euro/ha) per growth season / crop and the totals over the three year trial

KEYWORDS

Organic arable farming, farmyard manure, compost, cover crops.

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